

Resilient Multi-Tenant Network Programmability for Adaptive Service Placement

Timo Geier and Sebastian Rieger

Department of Applied Computer Science,
Fulda University of Applied Sciences, Germany

Email: timo.geier@cs.hs-fulda.de, sebastian.rieger@cs.hs-fulda.de

Abstract

In the increasingly dynamic world of network technologies, the ability to perform code updates quickly and reliably for multiple tenants is crucial to address the demands of modern network management and security in programmable networks. This paper presents an approach for resilient multi-tenant code updates focusing on adaptive network service placement. By extending our previously presented Orchestrator for Multi-Tenant Programmable Data Plane (PDP) Code Updates (OMuProCU), we not only enable seamless data plane code updates, but also ensure holistic and consistent network state updates without disrupting operations. Our approach adds state synchronization across multiple orchestrators as well as their components and addresses the coordination of network behavior in response to PDP code updates. We describe scenarios for accelerated containerized network functions migration in edge computing and 5G networks, which significantly benefit from our enhanced orchestration, and evaluate the benefits of resilient network state management in the improved orchestrator. Furthermore, the Quality of Service (QoS) of use cases in 5G networks and how they can benefit from our orchestrator are described. Our case studies, focusing on edge computing networks and integration into 5G infrastructures, outline OMuProCU's pivotal idea in fulfilling stringent QoS requirements emanating from varied use case demands, ranging from ultra-low latency to high throughput and reliability. This is evaluated by a Proof-of-Concept traffic application and a comparison with deploying CNF in a private and public cloud besides the accelerated CNF deployed by our framework. The solution aims to increase network resilience and flexibility, paving the way for adaptive, reliable state changes in an era where network programmability and multi-tenancy are in the forefront.

Keywords: Network Functions; Resilience; Multi-tenancy; Network Programmability; Hardware-accelerated Virtualization

1 Introduction

Network automation has evolved in recent years to support network programmability allowing fast and flexible code updates in programmable data plane (PDP) switches and network interfaces. Network programmability can be used to accelerate containerized network functions (CNFs) by offloading code into the PDP. An

architecture which supports these accelerated CNFs on programmable switches (PS) has been proposed, e.g., in [5]. While the network automation supports deep programmability of the network and rapid changes in the formerly static data plane logic, the connection between data and control plane still has to rely on network state being stored in ephemeral table entries (e.g., TCAM) or memory (e.g., SRAM). By enhancing our previously presented multi-tenant data plane code update orchestrator (OMuProCU [6]) to also support updates of these dynamic configuration values in the control plane, such as ARP, NDP or DNS lookup caches and runtime tables, e.g., routing or forwarding table entries, fast and seamless updates of the network's ephemeral state are enabled. The update mechanism goes beyond deploying only data plane code changes and allows more holistic and consistent (meaning integral and resilient) updates of the overall network state without disrupting its operation and ongoing transfers. Consequently, we also introduce resilient operation of OMuProCU to not only support seamless updates leveraging ECMP [7], but furthermore consider and mitigate outage of the orchestrator itself. This also includes synchronization of the state of multiple orchestrators and their components. Use cases for code updates and state changes related to device and network function migration in edge computing (EC) and 5G networks are described and discussed. The improved orchestrator is provided as open source¹ together with example scenarios described in this paper.

2 Related Work

In [12] the authors also described programmable data plane use cases for 5G and EC scenarios using a similar architecture compared to the one that is used in this paper based on our previous work [6]. The authors demonstrate the advantages of the architectural approach by deploying virtualized switches either on bare metal or in Docker containers, with and without P4 acceleration. However, the resilience of the architecture is not discussed, nor are resilient and adaptive updates of the surrounding network states considered for introduced code changes. A similar approach to use data plane acceleration techniques while ensuring isolation for mul-

¹<https://github.com/tiritor/OMuProCU>

multiple tenants is proposed by [8]. The authors focused their work on providing an approach which improves the manageability for system administrators, while our approach focuses on providing a secure and fast way for tenants to deploy their own accelerated CNFs with offloaded PDP code. [3] describes the problem of positioning VNFs of a Service Function Chain (SFC) in mobile EC infrastructures and a solution for proper SFC placement and migration by proposing an algorithm named Follow-Me Chain. The combination of a 5G framework and offloaded User Plane Functions are introduced in [10]. The proposed solution employs two P4 programs: one creates a simplified model data plane for easier control plane interaction, and the other optimizes performance on hardware switches to enhance speed and bandwidth. Additionally, microservices are introduced for tasks that exceed the capabilities of high-speed switch hardware. Resilience for PDP using P4, is, e.g., proposed in [9]. The authors present a mechanism leveraging SDN and P4 to calculate backup paths that can be used in case of a failure during data plane code updates. Nonetheless, besides the backup path the solution does not support updates of other network state data like runtime tables or caches in network devices. It also does not address 5G and edge scenarios for CNF mobility and migration. Previously, the potential of programmable networks to enhance network resilience was described in [15]. The paper focuses on the overall potential based on flash crowd simulations and does not contain network state change mechanisms. The same holds true for [14], although the paper uses a meta or global controller layer approach that can be compared to the one used in this paper for code update orchestration redundancy. Also, [11] introduced an approach named FELIX to implement rapid failure recovery in SDN networks by using pre-computed tactics for potential failures and fast activation at data plane speed. Scenarios and future directions for 5G use cases by using Tactile Internet are described in [4], [13] and [2]. They described future directions, issues and challenges as well as possible application use cases. Especially, [2] described the focus shift to 6G communication to support high QoS for Tactile Internet in EC area. Examples for QoS requirements and challenges for Tactile Internet for different use case scenarios with its performance metrics are described by [13] and [4]. Also, the authors in these contributions suggested potential solution or ways to solutions.

In contrast to the presented related work, this paper adds resilience to PDP for both the implemented orchestration layer and the code updates themselves. This way, resilience is also enabled during the updates by supporting pre- and post-update changes to nodes and links affected by the update, thus supporting consistent dependent network state changes. The application of these contributions is discussed for use cases in 5G and EC environments.

3 Resilience of Accelerated CNF Deployments

CNFs enable fast and resource-saving deployments of virtualized network functions (VNFs) as they possess less overhead compared to traditional VM-based deployments and are easier to manage thanks to prevalent container orchestration platforms. However, besides and also due to their performance advantage, they hold the disadvantage of having poor isolation. This represents a dilemma in multi-tenant environments where hardware-accelerated offloading functions, e.g., combined with CNF, are desirable, but have the side effect of decreased tenant isolation. Therefore, to accelerate CNFs in multi-tenant environments securely and deterministically, we proposed OMuProCU in previous related work. Nonetheless, the resilience of this orchestrator and surrounding network environment was not addressed and evaluated during its initial development. To enable a resilient approach for multi-tenant code updates in programmable networks, different ways and components that can fail must be considered and covered by appropriate safety mechanisms. Especially, if the network state is highly volatile, because the communication can move within the infrastructure, the resilience of deployed tenant appliances must be ensured. Therefore, the resilience of the following three areas will be introduced and discussed in this paper: Global Management Plane (GMP) with global orchestration and management, OMuProCU itself and its components, as well as functions of the network devices. Figure 1 shows these three different aspects in our testbed architecture.

Figure 1: Programmable network resilience areas.

3.1 Resilience of Global Management Plane

The GMP is the part of our approach which is responsible for the orchestration and management across a provider's infrastructure. It ensures a stable and secure rollout between multiple devices if used in ECMP-enabled network infrastructures. However, it possesses the disadvantage of centralizing the entire control plane for the initially proposed orchestration approach. If the centralized GMP fails or the connection to it is lost, different OMuProCUs can operate independently, but the global orchestration and management will cease to work, leading to a state drift and lack of coordination. Consequently, the GMP should be deployed as a distributed system which means that it should be deployed in parallel to the OMuProCU agents as shown in Figure 1. This allows redundancy

of the GMP agents but also leads to common challenges of distributed systems. The agents should only apply changes, if a quorum of GMP agents approves them. To know if adjacent agents are still running and working, they send heartbeats to each other. To limit write operations across an entire infrastructure and to prevent split-brain situations, the agents should be deployed in active or standby mode.

3.2 Resilience of OMuProCU

Besides the GMP, the orchestrator must be designed as resilient as possible and hence running on each device shown in Figure 1. Each OMuProCU has a critical time window (Code Update Step) where the packet processing is stopped as the PDP processing pipeline and its code is swapped and updated. It is crucial to ensure that the deployment process is resilient to potential failures that may occur during the rollout. Previous work has addressed this issue by developing methods for detecting deployment failures and ensuring proper rollback of partial changes during the update of programmable network devices. However, if a component or programmable device fails (e.g., is unavailable or has crashed), OMuProCU should stop the deployment process before the critical time window. To enable this, the OMuProCU management process should continuously monitor the state of all corresponding components.

Respectively, to enhance the resilience of the entire infrastructure, redundant devices with different paths can form a virtual logically centralized switch using Link Aggregation Groups (LAGs). This provides redundancy if the same accelerated CNF is deployed on different programmable devices on separate redundant paths and ensures appropriate failover mechanisms. Thanks to LAG, the load is distributed between these devices/paths with respect to the used distribution/ hashing algorithms. Furthermore, OMuProCU uses its rule updater component to allow faster, and more dynamic rule updates compared to regular non-programmable switches by using custom tables with fine-grained rules for specialized use cases of each tenant, which can now be updated, e.g., for traffic engineering, as described in 4. These fast inline table or cache updates can be issued by the tenants themselves (by altering their own tables) as well as from the orchestrator’s or provider’s holistic view across multiple affected tenants.

3.3 Resilience of Device Components

Besides the GMP and OMuProCU, components and running devices could also fail and must be therefore considered in a resilient design. Using redundant switches as a virtual switch can ensure failover. If components of the devices fail, this must also be detected, e.g., if a link fails due to a technical issue (link flapping or similar). However, a failed link may not be directly detected by the device itself, which means that the LAG as depicted in Figure 1 is not automatically reconfigured to set the corresponding link to inactive resulting in packets being lost.

As a countermeasure, an additional monitoring component which could be integrated in OMuProCU is needed to prevent such cases. Furthermore, OMuProCU should inform the GMP about corresponding events which subsequently update its topology and optimize its route configuration to prioritize an alternative route with the previously described fast rule (and table) update mechanism if necessary. Additionally, the GMP could also initiate a migration process to orchestrate the accelerated CNFs from the failed devices to other devices.

4 Resilience in Edge Computing Networks

Resilience of the previously described parts can be very important for different use cases. Accelerated CNF services could be deployed in a centralized form within a data center (DC). However, these services could introduce additional latency and increase the network utilization which also increases energy consumption. Deploying accelerated CNFs in EC networks can decrease the network load and the resulting latency by moving computations closer to the corresponding clients and leveraging excessive hardware offloading. However, the state of EC networks is volatile, because clients can move between different edge locations or network access points and roam across EC networks. In the following, a resilient approach to manage accelerated CNF deployment in an EC infrastructure will be proposed. Depending on the network’s requirements, different variants are possible, e.g., in a public, private or in a hybrid cloud. EC networks include mobile clients like cars, virtual reality (VR) or smart devices, that are moving between different locations and network access points, leading to the necessity to support roaming and handover.

4.1 Integration of OMuProCU in Edge Computing Networks

In previous papers, OMuProCU was primarily applied to DC networks. Consequently, deploying accelerated CNFs causes downtimes of the device where these should be running. Data center networks are typically more static than EC networks because there is no physical movement of endpoints compared to clients accessing EC networks. On the contrary, EC networks can be very volatile, e.g., contained resources are deployed very dynamically consequently raising the likelihood of frequent network state changes. Furthermore, virtual networks with dedicated CNFs and different guaranteed service levels can be created, updated and destroyed. Given these dynamic scenarios, OMuProCU can be used as an orchestrator to quickly and seamlessly update the surrounding network state and relevant devices. Additionally, security and privacy can be enhanced by reviewing and modifying the PDP code deployed by a tenant. Due to the explained fluctuations in edge networks, there is also a higher probability that entire virtual networks and accelerated CNFs will require relocation or updates. This

Table 1: Requirements of different use cases in programmable edge networks and resulting OMuProCU task prioritization.

Network Characteristics	VR Applications	Car-to-X Comm.	Smart Cities	Healthcare	Industrial IoT
Low Latency	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
High Bandwidth	✓	(✓)	✓	(✓)	(✓)
Scalability	(✓)	✓	✓	(✓)	✓
Mobility Support	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Security Features	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Energy Efficiency	(✓)	✓	✓	✓	✓
High Reliability	✓	✓	(✓)	✓	✓
Collaborative Intelligence	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
QoS Prioritization	Latency, Bitrade	Latency, Reliability	Reliability, Scalability	Reliability, Latency	Reliability, Latency
OMuProCU Tasks Prioritization	QoS Rules Modification, CNF Migration, Route Optimization	QoS Rules Modification, Route Optimization, CNF Migration	Route Optimization, QoS Rules Modification, CNF Migration	QoS Rules Modification, CNF Migration, Route Optimization	QoS Rules Modification, Route Optimization, CNF Migration

can also happen if a client moves to a different edge network area or to minimize power consumption in the infrastructure. An example of such a scenario is shown in Figure 2 where the previously described programmable devices and their connections are aggregated into a rectangle that resembles a virtual switch. The accelerated CNF depicted in Figure 2 is initially deployed on the uppermost programmable device where the client was previously located. However, as shown in the figure, the client has since moved to a new location on a base station connected to the lowermost programmable device. This could for example be the case if the client roamed between two mobile network segments and corresponding edge network locations. By migrating the CNF closer to the client's new physical location, the delay for latency-sensitive applications is reduced. Also, the overall network load is reduced as the client can access the CNF directly at the first hop, eliminating the need to send data over the backhaul. This is enabled by the orchestrator proactively modifying the rules and table/cache entries for the accelerated CNF communication to quickly avoid additional latency caused by the roaming client. This is especially useful, if low latency is required, e.g., for AR/VR or Car-To-X use cases. Accelerated CNF should be migrated as close to the client as possible, in this case adjacent to the nearby base station to which the client is now connected. Such events can be notified to the accelerated CNF by integrating a message queuing system into OMuProCU, whereas a message will be forwarded to its CNF for further decision-making, e.g., route optimization and moving or copying CNFs to a better location.

4.2 Integration in 5G networks

Edge computing approaches are used in recent mobile networks, e.g., 5G. Providers of 5G and beyond-5G networks can slice their network for applications of different tenants. As SDN and NFV are used in 5G networks,

Figure 2: CNF migration in an edge computing environment.

OMuProCU can also be applied to them. In our approach tenants can deploy their own CNFs into the infrastructure by using our orchestrator. If a client moves and is handed over to another mobile network or base station, these could be running redundant CNFs on multiple different "virtual" devices distributed across the providers' infrastructure. However, this approach can be very resource-intensive and also result in higher latencies which can negatively impact low-latency tenant applications, like VR/AR or Car-To-X communication. An example of an accelerated CNF could be an appliance that shares traffic information, such as sensor data from cars and nearby devices to find parking lots, get better traffic flow management or distribute a warning about approaching an emergency vehicle. Figure 3 shows the client roaming between different mobile stations and the connection to corresponding accelerated CNF being updated while the client moves. Therefore, each time it roams to a new base station or mobile network, the connection must be checked if it still meets desired requirements to ensure that the Quality of Experience (QoE) is not negatively affected. If not, the CNF must be migrated and all table as well as cache entries containing addresses of the roaming client proactively updated by OMuProCU. However, different use cases regarding edge network applications and their acceleration have different requirements as listed in Table 1.

For example, for VR/AR applications it is not important

Table 2: QoS requirements for Different Use Cases in Tactile Internet (based on [4] [13]).

Use Cases	Bitrate	Latency	Jitter	Reliability
VR Applications	Very high (< 250Mbps)	Very low ($1ms < d < 20ms$)	Minimal (< 5ms)	Extremely high (> 99.999%)
Car-to-X Comm.	Variable (10Mbps to several 100Mbps)	Extremely low (< 10ms)	Very low (< 5ms)	Extremely high (> 99.999%)
Smart Cities	Variable (several Kbps to several Mbps)	Medium to low (< 50ms)	Low (< 20ms)	High (> 99%)
Healthcare	High (10 – 25Mbps)	Low (< 100ms)	Moderate (< 30ms)	Very high (> 99.99%)
Industrial IoT	Variable (several Kbps to Mbps)	Low to very low (< 50ms to < 10ms)	Low (< 20ms)	Extremely high (> 99.999%)

to have high collaborative intelligence. Also, scalability and energy efficiency would be good, but are not essential requirements. Based on these individual requirements of different use cases, OMuProCU prioritizes its tasks Quality of Service (QoS) rules modification, CNF migration and route optimization. The overall goal of the tasks is to improve service quality, e.g., by differentiating and prioritizing services based on their QoS requirements, as also shown in Table 2. Besides modifying QoS rules in programmable network hardware, also path selection and routing can be optimized to improve service quality for different use cases. Additionally, the service quality can be significantly influenced by migrating the service or latency-sensitive parts of it closer to the user, i.e., near to the network edge. Typical requirements regarding QoS requirements for the different use cases can be found in surveys for tactile internet, e.g., [4] and [13]. Table 2 is based on respective definitions in these surveys. The necessity for tactile internet QoS requirements can be observed by looking at use cases like AR/VR. While existing AR/VR applications already require low latency and high reliability, for immersive VR these requirements are even higher leading to ultra-low latency and ultra-high reliability. This is due to the fact that for the VR scenario to get immersive, any stuttering or quality glitches would lead to the artificial environment instantly being revealed dissolving the immersion. Similarly, Vehicle-to-X communication benefits from tactile internet aspects since low-latency message transfer is essential for traffic information exchange or distance control, though different granularities of latency can be tolerated in this regard. Also, smart grid (electricity networks) require low end-to-end latency, needing fast update propagation for available energy, e.g., in case of fluctuating renewable energy sources or sudden power surges or demand. Typically, for these tactile applications, latencies below 1 ms are necessary. Such low latency budgets would be quickly exhausted in our experimental testbed, as even the local private cloud is in mean 0.375 ms away, as can be seen in Table 4. This holds especially true if multiple tenants increase the load on network paths leading to the service. Common network infrastructures are not designed to guarantee tactile internet requirements and are not responsive and reliable enough. Therefore, a combined solution as described for OMuProCU to en-

sure low latency using proper QoS rules in the network runtime state, optimized routes and adaptive CNF placement is necessary. This way, data of latency-sensitive use cases can be preprocessed near to the user while more data volume and velocity is offered in upstream stages as private and public cloud. Additionally, this supports higher security, as sensitive data is processed in a decentralized way holding data close to the user without aggregating it in centralized cloud infrastructures, as, e.g., beneficial for health or (I)IoT automation applications. This allows for the possibility to migrate the accelerated CNF closer to the client instead of only adapting the routes, network state tables or QoS levels. For Car-To-X communication other network characteristics are required. The high bandwidth characteristic depends on the data that should be sent, e.g., map or high-quality sensor data needing high bandwidth. Yet, in the case of sending only results of decisions to other clients, a high bandwidth is not necessary. In contrast to the VR/AR applications use case, high reliability as well as collaborative intelligence is necessary for this and the other use cases. Therefore, optimization task prioritization of OMuProCU also differs from the AR/VR use case. As described in Section 4.1, this could also be useful to save energy by reorganizing accelerated CNFs in a provider’s EC network. Consequently, the accelerated CNF can be optimized for each use case based on individual application requirements, e.g., by updating routing, state tables or QoS rules or by moving the entire accelerated CNF to another (closer) device. The described approach needs to include decision-making based on different use cases judging whether it is necessary to migrate the entire accelerated CNF or only update rules and network runtime state entries for, e.g., better routing to the CNF or better QoS. This decision-making can leverage Deep Learning and Generative AI approaches to assist these steps and optimize the placement of accelerated CNFs.

5 Evaluation

We evaluate two parts to show the resilience aspects as well as the importance of QoS requirements. First, network state resilience by using the new resilience extension of OMuProCU is evaluated which were described in Section 3. Afterwards, the QoS requirements are mea-

Figure 3: Client mobility in an edge computing environment.

sured by moving the CNF more near to the client and using the offloading functionality of the PS. The CNF is deployed as accelerated CNF using OMuProCU, in a private cloud environment using Charmed OpenStack and in a public cloud environment using AWS. An application using its own application protocol on top of UDP is used to simulate HTTP/3 (QUIC), streaming traffic or any connectionless application protocol. For both scenarios, we used a testbed consisting of four APS BF2556X-1T switches in the topology shown in Figure 4 using the Open-Tofino framework [1]. OMuProCU deploys and maintains the tenant code on all PS by deploying code updates to redundant orchestrators on all programmable network elements, as depicted in Figure 1 regarding GMP and OMuProCU resilience. The topology was selected to support two ECMP links between PS_1 and PS_3 . Also, the testbed is extended to have an outside connection as uplink for the second evaluation part.

5.1 Network State Resilience

First, the evaluation of the device component and network element resilience shown in Figure 1 will be addressed. These are important parts for resilient network state to ensure that the client roaming can be done without any large interference, e.g., an accelerated CNF migration is not necessary for the time being. Besides adding resilient orchestrators, OMuProCU was also extended to contain a rule updater, as described in the previous sections, to allow dynamic runtime updates of state tables and caches in network elements. This way, seamless failover of paths and timely consistent network state are now supported in the architecture.

Figure 4: Testbed for orchestration and network state resilience.

To test the new capabilities and evaluate a Proof of Concept, we deployed a CNF to PS_2 that is used by a client being connected to PS_4 . However, the client afterwards roams from PS_4 to PS_1 . In the topology the roaming leads to a longer path and corresponding latency for the client to access its associated CNF. Table 3 shows the higher latency for the client to access its CNF in

the *Before Update* column. After OMuProCU updated the rules and corresponding network state, the client accesses its CNF over the direct connection using the link from PS_1 to PS_2 and consequently the observed latency dropped in our measurements as can be seen in the *After Update* column in Table 3. Also, the standard deviation significantly decreased meaning that the jitter was smaller. Measurements were sampled 30 times before and after the update leading to mean and median values in the table. More importantly, the duration for the update process was measured. 60 updates were performed with a mean duration of 0.874 secs after which the client used the optimal path with a lower latency. This sub-second network state change of the corresponding runtime tables (forwarding and ARP table), is significantly faster compared to common default timeout values in forwarding information bases or ARP tables, commonly being defined around 2 to 5 minutes. Hence, as also enabled by SDN controllers, the network state can be timely controlled and updated after and according to tenant code updates on the programmable network elements. However, OMuProCU takes this concept further by orchestrating data plane code updates, network runtime state management and being resiliently designed itself.

Table 3: Path optimization orchestration results.

Statistics	Before update	After update	Difference
Mean	103.015 μ s	99.320 μ s	-3.587 %
Median	102.150 μ s	98.523 μ s	-3.552 %
Min.	96.750 μ s	93.945 μ s	-2.900 %
Max.	113.368 μ s	108.226 μ s	-4.536 %
Variance	19.785 μ s ²	11.937 μ s ²	-39.667 %
Stdev.	4.448 μ s	3.455 μ s	-22.326 %

5.2 QoS improvements by using the OMuProCU framework

The QoS in EC environments must be precisely considered ensuring a good Quality-of-Experience for the use cases as described in Section 4.2. To guarantee the desired QoS for the use case, the CNF cannot always be located in an environment far from the client, e.g., in a public cloud environment. So, a CNF could also be deployed in the same campus network, which is simulated in our case by using a private cloud. However, if the CNF is deployed on a private cloud environment located in the same campus network with the client, the QoS requirements could be too high to guarantee certain levels as introduced in Table 2. To show the improvement by moving the CNF near to the clients by using our orchestrator framework, the different location of the CNF will be evaluated as described above. First, the CNF will be deployed as accelerated CNF on a PS as in Section 5.1. Afterwards, the CNF will be deployed in a private cloud environment and finally in a nearby public cloud environment. For this, we use the same testbed from Figure 4 which was extended to possess an outside connection to a private cloud and public cloud environment. We use Charmed OpenStack for our private cloud environment,

while we used AWS as our public cloud operating an EC2 instance which is deployed in Frankfurt, as the nearest public cloud location to our testbed offering the lowest latency. Both instances in the cloud environments are micro instances using Ubuntu 24.04 with 1 vCPU and 1 GB RAM. The previous testbed as well as the used private cloud are grouped together to form a campus network as in typical EC environments. The client is still the same host being connected to a PS as in the previous experiment. The whole setup is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Testbed for UDP transfer sample in different locations.

In order to demonstrate the feasibility of streaming content or using HTTP/3 (QUIC) as a proof of concept, we have implemented an illustrative application that employs UDP as a transport protocol and a bespoke application protocol developed in-house. The application protocol comprises a type field (8 bits), a session ID field (16 bits), and the payload itself (the packet length is the maximum UDP packet length minus the length of the VXLAN header, which is 24 bits). A client and a server application were developed for this protocol, which enables communication between the two to generate traffic. Both are implemented in Rust to enable rapid traffic processing. The server implementation is operational as CNF in cloud computing environments as an accelerated CNF of a tenant. For accelerated CNF, the function utilized in Section 5.1 is extended to support the custom application protocol and will continue to be deployed on the PS₂. Experiments were conducted 10 times in succession to ensure reproducible results. Results are shown Table 4: Example UDP latency for different CNF location.

Statistics	Accelerated CNF	Private Cloud	Public Cloud (AWS Frankfurt)
Mean	0.047 ms	0.375 ms	3.497 ms
Median	0.051 ms	0.282 ms	3.205 ms
Min.	0.035 ms	0.170 ms	2.984 ms
Max.	1.214 ms	22.203 ms	32.829 ms
Variance	0.004 ms ²	0.812 ms ²	2.617924 ms ²
Stdev.	0.020 ms	0.901 ms	1.618 ms

in Table 4. The mean latency as well as all other statistics are showing the lowest latency when using the accelerated CNF. Especially, as expected, the variance is significantly higher when using the cloud computing environments. If the CNF is deployed in the private cloud, which is part of the client’s campus network, the latency as well as the standard deviation is significantly higher.

This means that for the CNF in the Private Cloud QoE could be negatively impacted depending on the use case. These effects are getting worse by deploying the CNF into the public cloud, where the variance is significantly higher. Nonetheless, this can still be within the QoS requirements mentioned in Table 2. However, it must be considered that the experiments were done by running one client and one server at the time. Therefore, the latency for the processing can be additionally significantly increased if more traffic will be generated by several clients.

The results show, that moving the CNF near to the client and using individual offloading by leveraging programmable network hardware and our orchestration framework can decrease the processing time. It also results into an improved placement next to the client. Therefore, this solution can improve the performance for several aforementioned use cases.

6 Discussion

When we presented OMuProCU on previous conferences, we received suggestions to develop enhancements to support resilience of the proposed architecture. The previous sections described and discussed corresponding extensions to support resilience in our OMuProCU instances running on programmable switches and adding the GMP to detect and compensate failures of individual OMuProCU instances. While developing these extensions, we observed that the overall resilience not only depends on the robustness of the orchestrator, but rather also on ensuring fast or even better proactive network state updates. Otherwise, during the rollout of new tenant code or even worse in the case of a possible rollback due to the update being interrupted or broken, transmissions and network services were negatively affected even though we introduced redundancy for the orchestration layer. Because we use programmable network devices, we were able to extend our orchestrator to include a rule updater, that can execute pre- or post-change operations as code updates are rolled out or rolled back. This includes changing tables and caches containing runtime information like routing or forwarding, ARP/NDP or DNS etc. In Section 5 we presented a Proof-of-Concept testbed where we could gather results to evaluate our concept. It demonstrates that being able to not only resiliently orchestrate tenant code updates on programmable network elements, but also correspondingly timely changing surrounding state configuration like forwarding or ARP tables, fast failover and optimal placement of network functions can be improved.

The rule updater is not constrained to control such runtime information on PS (utilizing standard P4 runtime), but can also be used to change corresponding network state tables and caches in hosts or other network devices (e.g., through CLI commands). As demonstrated in the evaluation and its results in Table 3, if a client has roamed to another component in the infrastructure, the network state may be updated if the previously uti-

lized route results in higher latencies while a shorter, more efficient route with lower latency is now available. This way, we did not only implement resilient orchestration as an extension to our approach we were previously asked for, but rather also improved the speed of network state failover, reducing service interruption and degradation. Hence, the developed solution is especially valuable in scenarios where large fluctuations in network state happen, like edge or mobile networks, as discussed in the previous sections. The staged approach, which supports data preprocessing in CNF in proximity to the user at the edge while leveraging local private or distant public cloud infrastructures for computationally or data-intensive tasks, allows for adaptive support for latency- or security-sensitive applications of multiple tenants in programmable networks managed by OMuProCU. The location experiments in Section 5.2 showed the significance of this fluctuation and how the accelerated CNF can mitigate this. While public cloud providers have access to a virtually limitless supply of resources, their latency and jitter are the highest of all. Especially, the jitter is significantly lower when accelerated CNFs are deployed even in comparison to private cloud environments. Also, if public cloud environments are used, the privacy concerns, e.g., for health applications, must be considered. Therefore, private cloud environments would consider both aspects and improve the QoE, but still the latency and jitter could be too high, especially for high traffic use cases, e.g., immersive VR or Car-To-X Communication. For other use cases in Tactile Internet like Smart Cities and Industrial IoT, the jitter is relevant as shown in Table 2. Therefore, it would be more appropriate to place the CNF in a Private Cloud. Moreover, if high reliability is important, e.g., for immersive VR and Industrial IoT, it would be recommended to place it next to the client. So, the accelerated CNF can mitigate these effects, but it must be always respected that the used programmable network hardware has only limited operations support and very limited resources, hence not all individual tenant functionalities can be offloaded. This way, not only lower latency for the overall service quality for different use cases is supported, but also higher bandwidths (due to less redundant transfers and upstream link utilization) as well as higher reliability can be achieved.

7 Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we considered different aspects of our multi-tenant programmable network code update approach (OMuProCU) regarding possible failures and introduced a more resilient design for related components. Furthermore, the resilience of accelerated CNF running on top of the programmable network devices we orchestrate can be ensured thanks to the newly developed extensions and enhancements of our orchestrator provided as open source. Accordingly, we discussed the resilience aspects as well as evaluated the benefits of these enhancements in edge and 5G infrastructures in combina-

tion with the integration of our OMuProCU approach into these infrastructures. Also, we have evaluated the latency impact for a proof-of-concept UDP application protocol to show the QoS improvements by using our orchestration approach when an accelerated CNF is deployed in an EC environment instead of a private or public cloud. Therefore, we have shown that our accelerated CNF can improve the QoE by improving the QoS requirements with lower latency, better jitter values or higher reliability. As next steps, we will evaluate the integration of other accelerator techniques, e.g., the usage of GPUs or XPU as well as look at the integration of other CNF isolation techniques like WebAssembly or microVMs. Since our orchestrator already supports the detection and assignment of individual acceleration techniques, this would allow further use cases using additional specialized hardware for the CNF besides programmable switches as presented in this paper.

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